

Cultivating Cultural Intelligence (CQ) through Experiential Learning-based English Instruction at Beijing Polytechnic

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Abstract:- The study aims to cultivate students' cultural intelligence (CQ) through experiential learning-based English instruction. The sample consisted of 53 students from two classes as the experiment and the control class respectively. The researcher used quantitative methods: the Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS) and a semi-structured interview (20 items) based on the CQS to collect data. The Scale's creators had done the validity test, of the CQS, so the researcher did the reliability test of the whole Scale and of the four parts of the Scale corresponding to the four dimensions of the CQ, and got Cronbach α of 0.886, 0.837, 0.742, 0.777, and 0.824 respectively. After collecting the data from the experiment class in the pre- and post-ODI phases respectively, the researcher did Wilcoxon Signed-rank Test, and found there was a difference in the experiment class students' CQ between pre- and post-OD intervention (the *p-value* was 0.000, and the *T (negative)* value was 0.00), and that the experiential-learning based English instruction helped cultivate the 4 dimensions of CQ, more in the experiment class than those in the control class.

Keywords:- Cultural Intelligence, Experiential Learning-Based English Instruction.

I. INTRODUCTION

China's economy has taken off since the reform and opening-up policy in 1978. Over 40-plus years of efforts, China's GDP has increased from 367.87 billion RMB, ranking No. 10 in 1978, to 98651.52 billion RMB, ranking No. 2 in

2019 (National Bureau of Statistics, China). When a country's economy develops to a certain level, it will attach great importance to the international communication of its culture, which is a common rule observed by countries on their way to rising [1].

One of the most significant trends since the turn of the century is the increasing depth of economic globalisation and global multi-polarization. The competition in international politics, the economy, and the military is gradually giving way to that of the soft power of culture and civilization [2]. Compared with China's economic ranks and political roles in the international community, its culture's international influence still needs improvement [3]. According to *the 2018 Report of Global Survey and Analysis of China's National Image* published by the Academy of Contemporary China and World Studies, the respondents' average impression of China's international image was only 6.2 points. The international image of a country is a reflection of the international community's comprehensive evaluation of a country's comprehensive strength, culture, politics, traditions, etc. A good international image is a prerequisite for China to promote Chinese culture's international influence [4].

China has been paying a lot of attention to the communication of the Chinese culture to the world, however, the result is not satisfactory. Here are some reasons.

First, cultures vary from country to country. there are inevitable cultural differences among different cultures. The *Strategic Evaluation Report of Culture's Going Global (2010)*, whose issuers include the Political and Strategic

Culture Professional Committee of Chinese Political Society, Current Affairs Report Magazine of the Publicity Department of the Central Committee of CPC, the Academy of Chinese Culture, and the Cultural Research and Development Centre of Beijing University, analysed seven problems or difficulties for Chinese culture to go global, and the top problem or difficulty is cultural differences. For many foreigners, Chinese culture is a heterogeneous culture. Therefore, they will intuitively have an attitude of exclusion towards Chinese culture and there will be severe cognitive dissonance ranging from ideas and philosophy to cultural products and cultural symbols [1].

Second, people who go abroad also have a lot to do with successful international communication of Chinese culture because, in most cases, culture is represented by people's words and behaviours [1]. When a Chinese travels abroad, he or she is a representative or a name card of Chinese culture. The international community knows about and understands Chinese culture by contacting different kinds of Chinese people, like officers, workers, tourists, etc. If Chinese people when going abroad don't behave appropriately, it would cause confusion among foreigners about the Chinese culture in ideal and that in reality. At the same time, if they don't know the behaviour norms of the foreign culture in which they are, they will not behave appropriately and may make mistakes or jokes. As a result, they will not be accepted by the locals, not to mention communicate the Chinese culture to the locals. In other words, if people want to behave appropriately, they must know both the culture where they are from and the culture where they are going. Otherwise, they will still behave as if they were in the culture they are from and may engage in some taboos. In other words, cultural knowledge is the basis for appropriate behaviour. However, even if people know the cultures well, the knowledge does not necessarily turn into behaviour if they don't have the willingness to do so or if they don't have the awareness of cultural cues during interactions with people from another cultural background.

Third, the cultural identification with the culture within a country is the basis for the culture's international communication (Bao, 2013). In the era of globalization, different cultural systems influence and permeate each other,

among which strong culture usually takes a dominating position [5]. In today's China, it is quite common to see young people celebrate Western festivals like Christmas, Valentine's Day, etc. when shopping malls also often offer bigger discounts to promote sales during the Western festivals. It is not uncommon for Chinese people to imitate American culture and follow their way of behaving, etc. Besides, according to a survey conducted among university students from over 10 Chinese universities, a large majority of respondents know a little about traditional Chinese culture, and most of their knowledge about culture only focuses on a few cultural representatives (like the 4 Great Ancient Chinese Inventions), while for other cultural representatives (drama, musical instruments), they have no knowledge at all [6]. All of this shows that many young people don't have a cultural identification with their own culture, which is also a barrier for Chinese culture to go global.

Fourth, in China, the number of intercultural communication talents is far from enough. Thanks to globalisation and technological development, there are more and more frequent cultural exchanges. If countries want to develop international cultural communication, they will be in great need of intercultural communication talent. However, China is lacking in such talent. Take translators and interpreters, who are usually capable of communicating cultures due to the inborn nature of their work, for example. According to statistics provided by the Translators Association of China, the number of professional translators and interpreters is only 60,000. There is a shortage of 100,000 high-level professional translators and interpreters [7].

In addition, the quality of intercultural communication talent is not satisfactory, either. We lack high-level talents who have a good knowledge of culture. For example, China's core cultural trade has been in deficit for many years, and one of the reasons is that it lacks professional talent who are experts both in culture and trade [4].

All in all, to improve the way Chinese culture is communicated internationally, there is a huge need for people who not only know a lot about different cultures but are also willing to put what they know into practise and are aware of

cultural cues that remind them they are in another culture and need to act properly. So, how to grow such talent is the research problem of the paper, and needs to be solved right away.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

When one country's culture spreads or transmits to another country's culture, inter-culture occurs [4]. When Chinese culture spreads to another country, there are interactions between itself and other cultures. Therefore, the international communication of Chinese culture involves intercultural communication.

2.1 Development of intercultural communication

After World War II, there was more global communication, diplomacy, and business, which created a need for a communication framework that was not solely based on linguistics [18]. The first researchers who came into the study of this field include Whorf [9], who, together with Sapir Edward, developed the Sapir-Whorf Hypothesis (Linguistic Realism), studying the relationship among language, culture, and thought and stating that the differences in how languages encode cultural and cognitive categories significantly affect the way people perceive the world around them [10].

The concept of "intercultural communication" was first introduced by Hall [11] in his book *The Silent Language*. There have been different definitions of intercultural communication. For example, according to Gudykunst and Kim [12], it is a mutual and symbolic process that concerns meaning attribution between individuals belonging to different cultural backgrounds. It has also been defined by Samovar et al. [13] as producing, transmitting, and interpreting symbols through verbal and non-verbal channels between people of different national cultures. Although there are differences in specific definitions, they all focus on communicative encounters between people or groups with different cultural backgrounds [14][15][16][17]. The communicative encounters include both verbal and non-verbal forms. According to the definitions, people who are good at intercultural communication must be familiar with their own

and other cultures. Usually, in intercultural encounters, someone or some people speak a language that is not their mother tongue [14]. This indicates that culture and language influence intercultural communication effectiveness, which again shows the significance of this study.

After the concept of "intercultural communication" was introduced, there appeared academic units which helped develop the field by publishing journals, textbooks etc.[18], like university classes and workshops at Pittsburgh University in the late 1960s [19], the intercultural communication division was founded by the International Communication Association (ICA) in 1970 and by the National Communication Association in 1975. During this period, there were no agreed-on theories developed, and the scholars just did research to better understand verbal and non-verbal aspects of intercultural communication [18].

Before the 1980s, the study of international communication was mainly in the USA and Japan. Since the 1980s, the world has seen an explosive study of intercultural communication [10], as researchers developed theories and measurement scales to investigate cultural characteristics with different methods in different countries. There is also research to differentiate cultural characteristics of Asian countries and redefine western-based paradigms of intercultural communication mainly influenced by US scholars [20]. But one thing must be pointed out: intercultural communication studies in other countries and regions are deeply influenced by theories developed in the USA.

2.2 Key research areas and theories in intercultural communication

Cultures in the world are complex with different characteristics. This, as a result, provides a lot of research perspectives for intercultural communication. However, there are three key research areas that have been the focus of intercultural researchers : identity, intercultural communication competence, and adaptation [21].

➤ *Identity*

In intercultural communication, there are two approaches to studying identity, namely the traditional approach and the modern approach [22]. The traditional approach takes communication as an internal source of conflict and identity stress during which the communicators try to reduce anxiety and fear [23]. Identity consists of several dimensions, including psychological and social factors [24]. Communicators' identities will be set up until they arrive at a mutual understanding and agreement on identity [25]. In contrast, the modern approach treats identity as animated and dynamic and will vary according to social context and time [26]. Under the two approaches, different types of identity were proposed, like ethnic identity [27] [28][29] personal identity [30][31] cultural identity [32][33], and political identity [34], etc. Some popular theories about identity include:

Social Identity Theory (SIT) studies both personal and social identity. The former includes identity characteristics that are personal and not connected with cultural or social groups. People keep and stress the identity that links them to a group and strengthens their self-image [35]. When they are in group-level communication, they stress the distinctiveness in favor of the in-group, and when the identity of the group is clear and outstanding, people's attitudes or behaviors are affected by this group identity [36]. SIT is actually a kind of categorization, which means people classify others based on the groups they belong to. Besides, the theory proposes that identity, which decides whether people are in a group or out of a group, will affect people's self-esteem, inter-group relationships, or conflicts [37].

Cultural identity is the stress people put on their emotional attachment or affiliation to a culture [38]. The more an individual is a core member of a culture, the more he/she understands the culture, including its beliefs, norms, symbols, etc. Cultural identity has two dimensions: value and salience [33]. Value is the expectation that a person has for the evaluation of their cultural identity, and salience means how strongly a person feels affiliated with the culture. Cultural identity is influenced by acculturation, cultural needs, cultural values, and various cultural communities [39]. Cultural studies research looks at things like cultural stereotypes and how

people are persuaded by them [39] and the political representation of national identity [40].

➤ *Intercultural Communication competence (ICC)*

Like in intercultural communication, there are various specific definitions for intercultural communication competence. It is generally defined as the knowledge, motivation, and skills to interact effectively and appropriately with members of a host culture [41][42][43]. That is to say, "effectiveness" and "appropriateness" are the two key elements of intercultural communication. Spitzberg [44] states that "Effectiveness is the successful accomplishment of valued goals, objectives, or rewards relative to costs." Appropriateness means that the valued rules, norms, and expectancies of the relationship are not violated significantly. Today, more and more researchers agree that intercultural communication competence is made up of cognitive, affective, and behavioral attributes [45].

The cognitive attribute refers to individuals' ability to perceive and accurately interpret verbal and non-verbal messages. This means the individual must have some knowledge of the host culture, like values, beliefs, family roles, and social communication norms. Chen [46][47] conceptualized the cognitive attribute as intercultural awareness. The measurement of it is culture-specific [48]. The affective attribute means the ability and motivation to appreciate, respect, and respond to the emotional and aesthetic experiences of host-culture members and accept cultural differences. Chen and Starosta [49] conceptualized it as intercultural sensitivity. The measurement is cultural in general and includes self-monitoring, open-mindedness, etc. [49]. The behavioral attribute emphasizes the ability to function in the host society. It means whether individuals are perceived as socially normal or healthy [50]. The measurement is a culture-general intercultural adroitness scale measuring flexibility, interaction relaxation, verbal and nonverbal message skills, identity maintenance, and interaction management [51].

➤ *Adaptation*

Cultural adaptation is a process. In intercultural communication, there are two models that arouse the most attention: Berry's [52] acculturation strategies and Kim's [53][54] cross-cultural adaptation model. Acculturation is a process in which cultures come into contact, and during this process, cultural learning occurs.

Berry's model has four strategies that a newcomer to the culture can have: assimilation, separation, marginalization, and integration. It involves how important the newcomer thinks his or her original culture and the host culture are or how much interest the newcomer has in his or her original culture and the host culture when entering the new culture. In assimilation, the individual reduces the importance of his/her original culture and attempts to identify with the new culture; in separation, the newcomer keeps the original culture and tries to avoid interaction with the new culture; in marginalization, the individual is not interested in either the culture; or in integration, the newcomer is interested in keeping the original culture and learning the new culture at the same time. People can choose a strategy based on whether they want to keep their original culture or adopt the dominant culture.

Kim's cross-cultural adaptation model [53][54] refers to adaptation as the dynamic process by which individuals, upon relocating to new, unfamiliar, or changed environments, establish (or reestablish) and maintain relatively stable, reciprocal, and functional relationships with those environments. It consists of several steps, including enculturation, deculturation, and acculturation of newcomers to the culture, and the final goal is assimilation into the new culture.

2.3 *Reflections on the above-mentioned theories*

First, Social Identity Theory and Cultural Identity Theory remind us that to strengthen international communication of Chinese culture, the Chinese people should have a strong identification with their own cultural identity, which is a precondition for successful international communication of Chinese culture [1]. However, this theory can not support the cultivation of talent for successful intercultural

communication since it has not touched on cultural awareness, willingness, knowledge, and behavior, which are what a successful talent needs in the intercultural communication field.

Second, the intercultural communication competence theories are clear about the three attributes of ICC, which gave inspiration to this researcher about the cultivation aspects of intercultural communication talent. However, they emphasize individuals' knowledge of the host culture instead of the communicator's knowledge of his or her own culture. If an individual doesn't know his/her own culture well, he/she cannot do well in the international communication of his/her own culture. Furthermore, this researcher observed that ICC was not treated as a whole in ICC theories. Even though more and more consensus has been reached about the affective, cognitive, and behavioral attributes as the three constituents of ICC, it seems the three attributes just exist separately. The measurement tools to test the three attributes are different. Finally, even if the individuals are good at the affective and cognitive parts of the ICC, they may not always behave appropriately when first entering a new culture. As a result, applying ICC theories to cultivate talents for intercultural communication in Chinese culture is insufficient.

Third, Berry's model is not without any limitations. In his model, it is a dichotomous choice (attempt to maintain the heritage or adopt the dominant culture), which indicates that in research, equal numbers of participants would be put in each category, which means not all the categories may exist as expressed [55][56]. Besides, it is also doubtful that a person would like to lose his/her original culture and not adopt a new culture at the same time to be a person without a culture [57]. If so, what is his or her cultural identity? Without a cultural identity, how can a talent communicate his/her culture to the world? There is no culture of free behavior [58].

As for Kim's model, the problem is that the final goal is to assimilate into the new culture. There has been research showing how immigrants to a new culture cannot or are unwilling to culturally adapt to the new culture [59][60][61][62][63]. If people were finally assimilated into the new culture, what would be the point of cultivating talent

to communicate the Chinese culture to the international community? There would be no Chinese culture in other countries at all since, based on this model, it would be assimilated into the new culture.

To sum up, although the above-mentioned theories bring inspiration to cultivating talents for intercultural communication, totally relying on them is not enough. This researcher needs to find some theory that not only cultivates individuals' original and host cultures so as to keep their original identity and communicate the Chinese culture at the same time but also focuses on treating knowledge, awareness, willingness, and behavior together as a whole. Moreover, it would be better if there was an instrument to measure it as a whole.

2.4 Cultural intelligence

The concept of cultural intelligence (CQ) was first presented by Earley and Ang [64]. It was based on the multi-dimensional intelligence model of Sternberg and Detterman [65]. Earley and Ang [64] define it as an individual's capacity to work and effectively manage social interactions in different cultural settings. It focuses on the ability to learn, evaluate, and behave effectively in a different situation characterized by cultural diversity [66] and helps people to learn continuously and better co-exist with individuals of different cultures.

Cultural intelligence has four dimensions: metacognitive CQ, cognitive CQ, motivational CQ, and behavioral CQ. The four dimensions make up the overall construct.

The awareness that people have for interacting with people from different cultures is referred to as metacognitive CQ. It is a mental process that people use to acquire and understand cultural knowledge and accomplish cognitive tasks like planning, monitoring, and adjusting mental models of cultural norms. It occupies a central position in this conceptualization of cultural intelligence [67]. Thomas et. al. [68] propose that it is this element that allows the emergence of cultural intelligence from the interaction of its three constituent elements. People with high metacognitive CQ are consciously aware of cultural differences and preferences before and during interacting with others. The value of

metacognition lies in the understanding of different levels of knowledge (the universal, the cultural-specific, and the setting-specific) and in how an individual acquires a new cultural perspective or how people from other cultures view themselves and make sense of another person's perspective.

Cognitive CQ refers to knowledge such as rules, norms, habits, and conventions that can be acquired through educational and personal experiences. It requires adjusting pre-existing concepts like why and how individuals perform in the way they do. In other words, the higher the cognitive CQ one possesses, the better one is at adjusting the conception of self and others. It stresses the importance of knowledge to the intellect.

The motivational quotient (MCQ) is the motivation that individuals have to learn and act effectively in various situations [69]. It shows the willingness or internal motivation to take part in intercultural experiences and learn how to handle the subtleties.

The behavioral CQ is the ability to demonstrate appropriate behaviors in interactions with different cultures. It includes both verbal and non-verbal behaviors. According to Earley and Peterson [70], a high-CQ person is able to figure out where new behaviors are needed and how to behave effectively.

To sum up, the four parts of CQ mean that if a person has a high CQ, they will be good at gaining cultural knowledge, be more willing to communicate with people from other cultures, and be able to adapt to a new culture and act in the right way. Moreover, they will be more aware of the cultural cues for intercultural communication. Such talent will do better in communicating Chinese culture to the world because the higher one's individual cultural intelligence is, the better he/she is at understanding and adapting to different cultures and at promoting cultural communication [70]. As a result, cultivating students' cultural intelligence could help solve the research problem of this study.

2.5 The Experiential Learning theory

Cultural intelligence can be developed [64][71][72][73][74]. CQ development is viewed as an ongoing process of developing metacognitive CQ, cognitive CQ, motivational CQ, and behavioral CQ [75]. This requires a process-oriented teaching and learning approach. Many articles in the fields of psychology, management, and education have proposed ways to develop cultural intelligence [70][74] [76][77]. Of all the approaches mentioned in these articles, experiential approaches have been acknowledged as particularly effective [78]. Besides, experiential approaches have the potential to bridge the gap between thought and action, moving from a pure cognitive focus to a stronger inclusion of behavioral aspects [79].

The Experiential Learning Theory was proposed by Kolb [80][81]. This theory emphasizes the process of learning. It believes that learning is a continuous process grounded in experiences, and that learning occurs through a sequence of four steps that create a learning cycle, as is shown in Figure 1. The four steps are: concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. Knowledge is gained through concrete experience and abstract thinking. Knowledge is changed through reflective observation and active experimentation.

Concrete experiences are the basis for reflective observation, which will be assimilated and distilled into abstract concepts from which new implications for actions can be formed, and these implications can be actively tested and serve as guides in creating new experiences [82]. Concrete experience refers to knowledge acquisition through sensory perception and direct practical experiences, namely experiential activities [83]. It is the basis of the learning process. Such experiences are intended to engage, motivate, and elicit an affective (feeling) response to the experience. "The more personally relevant the experience, the more likely the students' minds and emotions will be engaged." Activities providing students with concrete experiences include cases, simulations, in-class demonstrations, lectures with anecdotes, videos, learning about, and current news articles. [83]. These activities bridge students' perception gap between academic learning and the "real world".

Reflective observation is the intentional consideration of particular learning objectives. It creates meaning through observation and inward reflection. Careful objective reflection enables learners to objectively analyze their experiences, how to relate to other experiences, and how the experiences can be integrated into further learning stages. Activities in this regard are personal journals, directed writing, structured classroom discussion, and self-assessment.

Fig 1 Experiential Learning Cycle

In the abstract conceptualization stage, learners widen their learning by integrating theories and concepts in the process, and they can transform concrete experience into a symbolic representation through model-building assignments, critique of models and theories, and concept mapping.

Active experimentation involves testing or applying concepts in practice through the "real world". Activities include fieldwork, projects, "active" case studies, simulations, labs, and consulting projects. It emphasizes "doing".

Although experiential learning is acknowledged as effective in developing cultural intelligence, since cultural intelligence is new in China, whether the Experiential Learning Theory also helps cultivate Chinese students'

cultural intelligence has not been studied and needs research and practice.

Considering the importance of cultivating students' cultural intelligence in promoting Chinese culture to the world, this researcher aims to design a new kind of English instruction based on experiential learning to develop students' cultural intelligence.

Hence the research hypotheses are listed as follows:

H₁₀ There is no difference in Chinese students' cultural intelligence between the beginning and the end of the term.

H_{1a} There is a difference in Chinese students' CQ between the beginning and the end of the term.

H₂₀ The experiential learning-based English instruction doesn't help cultivate students' metacognitive CQ.

H_{2a} The experiential learning-based English instruction helps cultivate students' metacognitive CQ.

H₃₀ The experiential learning-based English instruction doesn't help cultivate students' cognitive CQ.

H_{3a} The experiential learning-based English instruction helps cultivate students' cognitive CQ.

H₄₀ The experiential learning-based English instruction doesn't help cultivate students' motivational CQ.

H_{4a} The experiential learning-based English instruction helps cultivate students' motivational CQ.

H₅₀ The experiential learning-based English instruction doesn't help cultivate students' behavioral CQ.

H_{5a} The experiential learning-based English instruction helps cultivate students' behavioral CQ.

III. METHOD

3.1 The model of the study

The research was a quantitative one and took one term. The researcher chose two classes with one as the experiment class and the other the control class. She used the Cultural Intelligence Scale in the form of a 7-point Likert Scale (with 1 standing for strongly disagreeing and 7 for strongly agreeing) to collect quantitative data of both classes about the four dimensions of cultural intelligence, i.e., metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral cultural intelligence at the beginning and the end of the term to get a clear idea of the

development of students' cultural intelligence and see if the experiential learning-based English instruction makes a difference to students' overall cultural intelligence and its four dimensions as well. Besides, the researcher made a semi-structured interview protocol based on CQS, and then interviewed 15 students from the experiment and the control class respectively to find out more about how the respondents' cultural intelligence was growing.

3.2 Population and sample

The population of the research consists 1295 students in Beijing Polytechnic, and the research sample consists of 53 students, 26 of whom fell into the experiment class and 27 the control class.

3.3 Data collection tools

Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS) and a semi-structured interview protocol based on the CQS were used in the research.

The Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS) was proposed and developed by Ang et. al. [66]. It consisted of 4 dimensions of cultural intelligence and had 20 items. It was in a 7-point Likert form with 1 standing for strongly disagreeing and 7 for strongly agreeing. Four items (1, 2, 3, 4) were about metacognitive cultural intelligence. Six items (5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10) were about cognitive cultural intelligence. Five items (11, 12, 13, 14, 15) were about motivational cultural intelligence, and five items (16, 17, 18, 19, 20) were about behavioral cultural intelligence. This scale was a 7-point Likert scale, with 1 for strongly disagreeing and 7 for strongly agreeing. The creator of the CQS did the validity test. CFA demonstrated good fit of the four-factor model to the data: $\chi^2 (164df) = 822.26$, NNFI = 0.91, CFI = 0.92, SRMR = 0.06, and RMSEA = 0.08 ($p < 0.05$). Standardized factor loadings for items in the four scales (0.52–0.80) were significantly different from zero (t-values: 9.30–17.51, $p < 0.05$). The four factors had moderate inter-correlations (0.21–0.45) and acceptable variances (0.75–1.03). The corrected item-to-total correlations (0.47–0.71) for each subscale showed that there were strong relationships between the items and their scales, which supported the fact that the test was internally consistent.

The CQS creator also collected additional data from Singapore and the USA to assess the generalizability of the CQS across samples, time and countries with three cross-validation samples.

Cross-Validation of the Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS) across samples. CFA on the first cross-validation sample (N = 447 Singapore undergraduates, 70% female, mean age 20) showed good fit for the four-factor model: χ^2 (164df) = 381.28, NNFI = 0.96, CFI = 0.96, SRMR = 0.04, and RMSEA = 0.05 ($p > 0.05$). Standardized loadings (0.50–0.79) were significantly different from zero (t-values: 8.32–12.90, $p < 0.05$), with moderate correlations between factors (0.23–0.37) and acceptable variances (0.87–1.05). Corrected item-to-total correlations for each subscale (0.46–0.66) showed strong relationships between items and their scales, which supports internal consistency.

Generalizability of the Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS) across time. A subset of respondents from the Singapore cross-validation sample (N = 204, 76% female, mean age of 20) took the CQS again four months later. The researcher examined T1–T2 longitudinal measurement invariance using CFA and an augmented covariance matrix as input (rather than a multi-sample approach) to account for time-wise correlated errors (Vandenberg and Lance, 2000). The CQS researcher used a 20-item by two-measurement occasion matrix and specified eight latent variables (four T1 CQ factors and four T2 CQ factors), with unique variances of identical items correlated across time. Following the procedure suggested by Vandenberg and Lance (2000), they began with a correlated four-factor model with no constraints (parameters at T1 and T2 freely estimated). Results demonstrated acceptable fit (Model A: χ^2 (692df) = 981.18, NNFI = 0.94, CFI = 0.95, SRMR = 0.06, RMSEA = 0.04), suggesting that the four-factor model held across the two-time periods. They then tested two alternative models. The χ^2 difference between Models A and B (factor loadings constrained to be invariant) failed to reach significance ($\Delta\chi^2$ (16df) = 22.79, $p = ns$), providing strong support for invariance in factor loadings across T1 and T2. The χ^2 difference between Models B and C (item intercepts constrained to be invariant) also failed to reach significance

($\Delta\chi^2$ (14df) = 17.59, $p = ns$), providing support for item intercept invariance.

The generalizability of the Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS) across countries. They looked at how the CQS matched up with a group of US undergraduates (N = 337, 55%).

Using sequential tests of model invariance, the Singapore cross-validation sample (N = 447) was found to be female, with a mean age of 22 (Byrne, 1998). Model A (four factors with loadings freely estimated across samples) demonstrated good fit: χ^2 (328df) = 723.23, NNFI = 0.96, CFI = 0.97, SRMR = 0.05, RMSEA = 0.05, indicating equivalence in a number of factors.

They tested two alternative models. The χ^2 difference between Models A and B (four factors with loadings forced to be invariant) failed to reach significance ($\Delta\chi^2$ (16df) = 13.74, $p = ns$), providing strong support for invariance in factor loadings across settings. The χ^2 difference between Models B and C (four factors with factor covariances forced to be invariant) failed to reach significance ($\Delta\chi^2$ (10df) = 17.96, $p = ns$), supporting invariance in factor covariances. In sum, multiple group tests of invariance demonstrated the same four-factor structure holds across the two countries.

Cultural Intelligence was new to the Chinese, and so was the CQS. To make sure the data gathered from the CQS was trustworthy, this researcher conducted a reliability test of the CQS. To make sure the scale could be understood well in the reliability test, this researcher, who was an English major passing the National Test for English Majors Level 8 by the Ministry of Education and awarded the International Conference Interpreter Certificate by the European Commission, translated the English version of the scale into Chinese, and then the researcher asked another translation major colleague, who was awarded China Accreditation Test for Translators and Interpreters Level 2 by Ministry of Human Resources and Social Security, to translate the Chinese version into the English version. Then this researcher asked an English native speaker who worked for Beijing Polytechnic to see if the translated English version of the scale and the original English version of the scale were equivalent in the meaning.

The native speaker gave a positive answer, which meant the translated Chinese version of the scale could be applied to the potential Chinese respondents. The Cronbach alpha of the Scale as a whole and its four subscales corresponding to the four dimensions of the CQ were 0.886, 0.837, 0.742, 0.777, and 0.824 respectively, which meant that the Scale was reliable.

The semi-structured interview based on the CQS had 20 questions covering all the four dimensions of cultural intelligence, among which 14 were semi-closed questions and 6 were 5-point Likert scale questions about the respondent's knowledge of legal and economic systems of other cultures; rules (e.g., vocabulary, grammar) of other languages; the cultural values and religious beliefs of other cultures; the marriage systems of other cultures; the arts and crafts of other cultures; and the rules for expressing nonverbal behaviors in other cultures.

Fourteen questions were in semi-structured form, i.e., students were asked to give either "Yes" or "No", and if the answer was "Yes", they were asked to give an example to support their answer. The researcher counted the number of "Yes" and of the examples to each Yes answer to each question at the beginning and end of the term.

3.4 Data analysis

3.4.1 Data analysis of the experiment class at the beginning and the end of the term

The researcher first did the normality distribution test, finding that both data collected through the CQS at the beginning and the end of the term were not normally distributed. Considering that the sample size in the experiment class was less than 30, the researcher used Wilcoxon Signed-rank Test to analyze the data. The p value is 0.000, and the T (negative ranks) is also 0.00. The researcher also calculated the median increases of each item in the CQS, finding that the median of 16 items increased and four remained the same, but none decreased.

The researcher then analyzed the data collected by the interview. At the beginning of the term, the number of "Yes" answers to each of the 14 semi-structured items was 7, 3, 7, 5, 5, 4, 7, 3, 3, 6, 4, 2, 6, 2 respectively. At the end of the term, the number increased to 12, 11, 11, 10, 13, 12, 13, 13, 13, and 12, 12, 11, 14, 12. Besides, the examples given by the respondents at the end of the intervention were richer and covered more cultural aspects.

3.4.2 Data analysis of the control class at the beginning and the end of the term

The control class used the traditional lecturing English instruction. The researcher calculated the median increases of each item in the CQS, finding that the median of 13 items increased, the median of 6 items remained the same, and the median of one item decreased.

The researcher then analyzed the data collected by the interview. At the beginning of the term, the number of "Yes" answers to each of the 14 semi-structured items was 5, 3, 5, 4, 3, 5, 3, 5, 3, 5, 4, 3, 5, 2, respectively. At the end of the intervention, the number increased to 11, 11, 10, 10, 9, 9, 10, 10, 10, 8, 7, 8, 9, 7. Besides, the examples given by the respondents at the end of the intervention were richer and covered more cultural aspects.

3.4.3 Data comparison between the experiment and the control class

First, data collected through CQS. The mean of the medians of the experiment class was 4.75 at the beginning of the term, and 5.8 at the end of the term. The increase was 1.05. The mean of the medians of the control classes was 4.1 at the beginning of the term, and 4.7 at the end of the term. The increase was 0.6. Compared with the mean increase, it was clear that the overall cultural intelligence of both the experiment and the control class was improved. However, the increase was much sharper in the experiment class than in the control class. The metacognitive mean of the medians of the experiment class in the pre-ODI phase was 5.5, and in the post-ODI phase it was 6. The increase was 0.5. However, in the control class, the metacognitive mean of the medians of the control class at the beginning of the term was 4.5, and at the end of the term, it was 5.375. The increase was 0.875. That is

to say, even though the experiential learning-based English class helped students improve their metacognitive CQ, the improvement was less than what was seen in the control class.

The cognitive mean of the medians of the experiment class at the beginning of the term was four and at the end of the term, it was six. The increase was 2. However, in the control class, the cognitive mean of the medians of the control class at the beginning of the term was 3.8, and at the end of the term, it was 4.2. The increase was 0.4. The students' cognitive cultural intelligence grew more in the experiment class. The motivational mean of the medians of the experiment class at the beginning of the term was 4.67, and at the end of the term, it was 5.33. The increase was 0.66. However, in the control class, the motivational mean of the medians of the control class at the beginning of the term was 4.17, and at the end of the term, it was 4.58. The increase was 0.41. The students' motivational cultural intelligence grew more in the experiment class. The behavioral mean of the medians of the experiment class in the pre-ODI phase was five, and at the post-ODI phase, it was six. The increase was 1. However, in the control class, the behavioral mean of the medians of the control class at the beginning of the term was 4, and at the end of the term, it was 4.8. The increase was 0.8. The students' behavioral cultural intelligence grew more in the experiment class.

Second, data collected through semi-structured interview. The interview data collected from the experiment class and the control class respectively at the beginning of the term and the end of the term showed that students' overall Cultural Intelligence and the four dimensional cultural intelligence were cultivated. However, looking deeper into the data of both classes, the researcher found that the increase in the number of yes answers to each item in the experiment class was 5, 8, 4, 5, 8, 8, 6, 10, 10, 6, 8, 9, 12, 10, and that in the control class was 6, 8, 5, 6, 6, 4, 7, 5, 7, 3, 3, 5, 4, 5. Except the metacognitive cultural intelligence, the number of yes answers to the motivational and the behavior cultural intelligence expanded more in the experiment and the control class.

IV. FINDINGS

The research contributes to several findings. First, there was a difference in Chinese students' CQ between the beginning and the end of the term. Second, the experiential learning-based English instruction helped cultivate students' metacognitive CQ. However, compared with the control class, the experiential learning-based English instruction didn't improve students' metacognitive CQ more. Third, the experiential learning-based English instruction helped cultivate students' cognitive CQ. Fourth, the experiential learning-based English instruction helped cultivate students' motivational CQ. Fifth, the experiential learning-based English instruction helped cultivate students' behavioral CQ.

V. DISCUSSION

5.1 The experiential-learning English instruction makes a difference in students' cultural intelligence (CQ).

Both experiential-learning-based theory and Cultural Intelligence Theory favor a holistic approach with the learner at the center, encouraging active learning and aiming for an integrative and transformative experience [84]. Both support processing development [85]. This made it easier to use experiential learning-based English instruction to help students develop their cultural intelligence. At the concrete experience period of the experiential learning theory, the researcher showed cases of misunderstandings in cross-cultural communication, gave lectures about cultures in different countries, or guided the students to discuss their experiences of interaction with foreigners when travelling abroad. During this process, students grasped cross-cultural knowledge about cultural rules, norms, and so on, and this helped improve students' cognitive cultural intelligence. After learning the experiences, in the next round of reflective observation, students either wrote journals independently to reflect on the reasons for the misunderstanding based on the previous phase of concrete experience or had an in-class discussion to analyze the reasons behind the misunderstanding. In this period, cultural conflicts began to pop up. Students found something that was quite different from their own culture. Learning was propelled by conflicts, differences, or disagreements. The tensions caused by the conflicts, or

differences, or disagreements were resolved in the iteration of movement back and forth between opposing modes of reflection and action and feeling and thinking (Passarelli & Kolb, 2011). As a result, by self-reflecting or discussing with others, students gradually formed the awareness of cross-cultural communication deep in their minds, and their future actions in intercultural communication scenarios were also influenced, which in turn cultivated students' metacognitive and behavioral cultural intelligence.

In the abstract conceptualization period, based on their reflection or analysis of the reasons for misunderstandings, students began to do critical thinking by comparing differences between cultures in a systematic way and forming a specific cross-cultural concept and a cultural model. In this way, students deepened not only their understanding of cultural knowledge but also their cross-cultural thinking or awareness. As a result, during the model or concept forming process, both their cognitive and metacognitive cultural intelligence were improved. In the active experimentation period, students put what they learnt or reflected into action by role-playing in and after class, or by practicing with foreign friends after class, if they had some friends from other cultures. In this way, students' behavioral cultural intelligence was directly cultivated, and during the process, since they stepped out into a new world of behaving in a different culture, their motivation to engage in cross-cultural communication was also increased or boosted. Finally, the teacher gave feedback whenever students showed their understanding, knowledge, or cultural performance. The feedback helped students to better understand their progress and weaknesses, which in turn helped students' future learning in the next learning cycle.

To sum up, the experiential-learning-based English instruction focused on the dynamic learning process during which students' whole cultural intelligence made a difference compared with that at the beginning of the term. This could be seen from the data results that were gained after the Wilcoxon Signed-rank test. According to the Wilcoxon Signed-rank Test, if the p value is less than 0.05 and if the T value absolute, be it the positive or the negative one, is smaller than the critical value, the null hypothesis will be rejected. As was shown in 3.4.1, the p value is 0.000, and the T (negative) value is also

0.00 less than the critical value when the number of the matched data group is 20. This means that H_{1a} There is a difference in Chinese students' CQ between the beginning and the end of the term is supported.

5.2 The experiential-learning English instruction helped cultivate students' metacognitive cultural intelligence.

At the beginning of each class, in the concrete experience period, the researcher gave students one or two cases, either in written or video form, falling into a certain cultural category, including cultural values: individualism versus collectivism; relationship specificity and diffusion; gender; power distance; uncertainty avoidance; long-term versus short-term orientation; time and work/study; intercultural communication psychology and attitude; intercultural behavior (verbal or non-verbal) – religious customs, taboos, salute; cultural adaptation – appearance (clothing), face and negotiation; food and drinks; and family. Sometimes, when students had similar experiences when travelling abroad or having intercultural exchanges, they were also invited to share their experiences. In some cases, students echoed the materials provided by the teacher with news articles they had read before. Such cases or the content carried in the materials always gave students some cultural shock, since what they saw or read from the cases was different from their life in China. Take the power distance, for example. In the case provided by the researcher, the young just called the elderly by the latter's given name, which was quite different from China. Students had a first impression of the cultural difference or shock during this period, which directly touched their cultural awareness. Then in the reflection observation period, with the cultural shock in their mind, students were guided to have an in-class discussion and share their thoughts and analyze the reasons for the cultural shock. During this process, they gradually formed and deepened the awareness that cultures in different countries or nations were different. When interacting with others, they would not assume that their culture was universal. Instead, they would respect the cultural differences, be aware of the cultural knowledge they were using, and adjust the cultural knowledge they were using based on what culture they were interacting with, which was seen from their role-play performance in the active experimentation period. Besides, after discussing the cases, students formed the concept of hierarchy and power

distance, which was an important concept in intercultural communication. Such a concept would guide their future intercultural communication in turn, during which the concept was reinforced in their minds. As a result, their metacognitive cultural intelligence was cultivated. At the beginning of the term in the experiment class, the median of the metacognitive cultural intelligence data was 5.5, while at the end of the term, the median increased to 6. In other words, the experiential learning-based English instruction helped cultivate students' metacognitive cultural intelligence. Hence H_{2a} was supported.

However, one interesting finding was that compared with the control class, the increase in the metacognitive cultural intelligence of the experiment class under the experiential learning-based English instruction was not as much as that of the control class.

This finding was supported by a smaller increase in the mean of metacognitive CQ medians in the experimental class compared to the increase in the control class. The mean of the four metacognitive cultural intelligence medians at the beginning of the term in the experiment class was 5.5, and after the intervention, the mean was 6. The increase was 0.5. However, in the control class, the mean of the four metacognitive cultural intelligence medians was 4.5, and at the end of the term, it was 5.375. The increase was 0.875. To find out the reason, the researcher checked her feedback to the students during the reflective observation period, and more than half of the students were marked once or twice as either having concerns about joining in the discussion or lacking confidence in the in-class discussion, which was an important way to find the reasons for cultural misunderstandings shown in the cases due to limited language proficiency. For example, one feedback was "Xuebing" (the name of the student), feel free to share your thoughts with your partners." "Zikang" (the name of the student), don't worry about making mistakes when expressing your ideas." According to Hall (1992), communication was an internal source of conflict and identity stress during which the communicators tried to reduce anxiety and fear. As a result, their attention was drawn more to the English language quality, focusing more on how to express themselves clearly than on fully immersing themselves in thinking about the reasons for the cultural misunderstanding,

which adversely impacted the development of the metacognitive cultural intelligence. Besides, according to the Social Identity Theory, the identity that decides whether people are in a group or out of a group will affect people's self-esteem, inter-group relationships, or conflicts (Roozen & Shulman, 2014). Students who were low in language proficiency felt embarrassed in a group because of their low contribution to the discussion, and this also impacted the development of metacognitive cultural intelligence. However, in the control class, students just listened to the teacher, and they didn't need to worry about expressing themselves or discussing questions or their identity in a group. Their attention was fully drawn to the cases, or they could think about the cases fully by themselves. Such quietness or a stable mind state helped them develop more metacognitive cultural intelligence.

This indicated that students' language proficiency would influence the cultivation of the metacognitive cultural intelligence since students couldn't be fully immersed in the discussion and express what they thought about, and they suffered from identity stress.

5.3 The experiential-learning English instruction helped cultivate students' cognitive cultural intelligence.

At the beginning of the class, in the concrete experience period, when students read the cases, they not only felt the cultural differences or cultural shock but also learnt how people in other cultures behaved verbally or non-verbally, what perspectives they were taking when treating some issues, and so on. This is a direct way of getting knowledge, too. Besides, in this phase, teachers gave lectures directly about cultural knowledge, like cultural values, cultural behavior, or practice, which also broadened students' horizons. Actually, besides cases and lectures, the researcher also referred to other different ways to facilitate students' access to cultural experiences like watching videos, discussing personal experiences or current news articles. In this way, students collected cultural knowledge in pieces. After having a reflective observation period where students shared thoughts or wrote journals about their thoughts, students gradually organized their thinking, and in the abstract conceptualization period, students found it easier to build cultural concepts or

models or give critiques of certain cultural theories. In this process, the students' cultural knowledge was enriched. Therefore, students' cognitive and cultural intelligence were cultivated.

Another point worth paying attention to was that during the abstract conceptualization, students built the cultural concepts or models or gave critiques of certain cultural theories. In this process, they inevitably compared Chinese culture with other cultures. As a result, when they absorbed foreign cultures, their own cultural identity was also reinforced. Social identity theory and cultural identity remind us that to strengthen international communication of Chinese culture, the Chinese people should have a strong identification with their own cultural identity, which is a precondition for successful international communication of Chinese culture (Bao, 2013). Therefore, the abstract conceptualization period not only helped cultivate students' cognitive cultural intelligence but also laid a sound foundation for the international communication of Chinese culture by stressing students' own cultural identity.

The development of students' cognitive and cultural intelligence could be proved by the research data. The median of the cognitive cultural intelligence dimension at the beginning of the term was four and was six at the end of term. Such an increase in the median means the experiential learning-based English instruction helped cultivate students' cognitive CQ. Hence, H_{3a} was supported.

5.4 The experiential-learning English instruction helped cultivate students' motivational and behavioral cultural intelligence.

Experiential approaches have the potential to bridge the gap between thought and action, moving from a pure cognitive focus to a stronger inclusion of behavioral aspects (Foster, 2000).

In the research, after the concrete experience, reflective observation, and abstract observation periods, students accumulated knowledge about cultural differences and what they should pay attention to when dealing with different cultures. At the same time, due to the cultivation of

metacognitive cultural intelligence, they were aware of using different cultural knowledge when interacting with people from different cultures and understood the necessity to adjust cultural knowledge when interacting with people of different cultural backgrounds. What they needed to do next was to put what they had learnt into practice to make sure their cultural intelligence was really cultivated. So in the active experimentation period, the teacher designed various activities for students to practice what they had learnt, including field work or active case studies, namely to put what was learnt into practice in communication with foreigners. In the experiment class, some students had a foreign pal, which facilitated their better understanding of what had been learnt and the assessment of their cross-cultural behavior. Most of the time, the researcher asked students to role-play the cases used in the concrete experience period. In the role-play, students were expected to behave appropriately in the situation, as shown in the cases. One thing that needs paying attention to was that, due to the influence of the Chinese face (*mianzi*) culture, there were students who were too shy or not confident enough to participate in active experimentation. Therefore, the teacher had to use encouraging words or gestures to help students overcome their shyness or build up the confidence to act out for themselves. According to the feedback of students, they always had a sense of achievement after the field work or role-play. For example, one student wrote, "I was very shy at first, but my teacher encouraged me to move. I was shy about refusing the teacher, so I tried acting the case out with my partners. Finally, we made it, and I felt so good." Another student wrote, "I like the role-play part very much when I act appropriately according to what I learnt from the class, like changing my body gestures or speaking tones, etc. I felt so proud of myself. This gave me more confidence that I can deal with people from different cultures." Such words, together with the data collected from the experiment class, showed that students' motivational and behavioral cultural intelligence were cultivated. Besides, the median of the motivational cultural intelligence dimension in the pre-ODI phase was four points out of five and was five in the post-ODI phase. Such an increase in the median means the experiential learning-based English instruction helped cultivate students' motivational CQ. Hence, H_{4a} was supported. Besides, the median of behavioral cultural intelligence at the pre-ODI phase was 5 and was 6 at

the post-ODI phase. Such an increase in the median means the experiential learning-based English instruction helped cultivate students' behavioral CQ. Hence H_{5a} was supported.

5.5 The experiential-learning English instruction helped cultivate students' cognitive cultural intelligence more than the control class.

The cognitive mean of the medians of the experiment class at the beginning of the term was four, and at the end of the term was six. The increase was 2. However, in the control class, the cognitive mean of the medians of the control class at the beginning of the term was 3.8, and at the end of the term it was 4.2. The increase was 0.8. That is, the experiment students' cognitive cultural intelligence grew more.

5.6 The experiential-learning English instruction helped cultivate students' motivational cultural intelligence more than the control class.

The motivational mean of the medians of the experiment class at the pre-ODI phase was 4.67, and at the post-ODI phase, it was 5.33. The increase was 0.66. However, in the control class, the motivational mean of the medians of the control class at the beginning of the term was 4.17, and at the end of the term, it was 4.58. The increase was 0.41. That is, the English classes based on the experiential learning theory helped students' motivational CQ grow more.

5.7 The experiential-learning English instruction helped cultivate students' behavioral cultural intelligence more.

The behavioral cultural intelligence mean of the medians of the experiment class at the beginning of the term was five, and at the end of the term was six. The increase was 1. However, in the control class, the behavioral mean of the medians of the control class at the beginning of the term was 4, and at the end of the term it was 4.8. The increase was 0.8. That is to say, the English lessons based on hands-on learning helped students develop their behavioral CQ more.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PRACTITIONERS AND RESEARCHERS

According to the research, the experiential-learning-based English instruction made a difference in students' overall cultural intelligence. It helped cultivate students' metacognitive cultural intelligence, cognitive cultural intelligence, motivational cultural intelligence, and behavioural cultural intelligence.

However, there are several limitations to the research. First, the research was only a case study. Therefore, there is a generalization limitation. Second, the sample was conveniently chosen. All the students in both the experiment and the control class were the researcher's students. The teacher-student relationship might facilitate the research in several ways, such as better interaction and cooperation when the research is ongoing.

There are several points that haven't been touched on in the research. For example, what is the relationship among the four dimensions of cultural intelligence, namely metacognitive cultural intelligence, cognitive cultural intelligence, motivational cultural intelligence, and behavioral cultural intelligence? How do they influence each other? Besides, according to the Experiential Learning Theory, learners could be divided into four categories based on their approach to obtaining knowledge, i.e., diverges, assimilators, converges, and accommodators. Diverges like learning through concrete experience and process learning by means of reflective observation. They are good at imagination and awareness of meaning and values. They are more likely to have a wide range of cultural interests and be interested in people. Accommodators are good at learning from "hands-on" experience. They like learning knowledge through concrete experiences but prefer to process it through active experimentation. They feel good with people but can sometimes become impatient. Assimilators like learning through abstract conceptualization and processing it with reflective observation. They are good at forming theoretical models, but don't pay much attention to people. They favor ideas and abstract concepts. The converge approaches knowledge through abstract conceptualization. However, they

favor processing learning through active experimentation. They prefer to deal with technical tasks and problems, and they don't like to deal with interpersonal and social issues. Their strength lies in solving problems, making decisions, and the practical application of ideas. How will the different learner styles influence the cultivation and development of overall cultural intelligence and its four dimensions? In addition, students in the research don't have strong English proficiency, which impacts their performance in different class activities. How will second-language proficiency influence students' development of overall cultural intelligence and its dimensions in second-language classes? Finally, in the research, several students had overseas travelling experiences before they were admitted into Beijing Polytechnic or had a foreign pal. How will international contact influence the development of cultural intelligence? The researcher suggested that all the questions mentioned above could be studied further and fill in the gap of the study.

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